

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OSHOTA****FIRST NAME: OLUWOLE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 12%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. A research question should tie together the three essences of research. According to Turabian in *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, these are? Choose the correct answer from the below options.
- The topic the researcher is interested in working on, what the researcher wants to discover, and the research's significance.**¹
- The topic the researcher is interested in working on, what the researcher wants to avoid discovering, and the research's significance.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 21.

- The topic the researcher is interested in working on, what the researcher wants to discover, and the research's non-significance.
 - The topic researcher is not interested in working on, what the researcher wants to discover, and the research's significance.
2. Contents organization is an essential component of the dissertation research. In *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research*, Sampson stressed schema importance as “one of the first tasks for doctoral students is to develop a schema for their dissertation research.” Therefore, assembling material information and data that belongs together succinctly is critical. How relevant is schema development? Choose the correct answer from the below options.
- Specific schemata are connected to derive a higher-order schema. For example, the chapters and sections of the dissertation are connected to derive the higher-order schema of dissertation organization.²**
 - Specific schemata are not connected to derive a higher-order schema. For example, the chapters and sections of the dissertation are not connected to derive the higher-order schema of dissertation organization.
 - A procedural schema is not essential in understanding the relationships among the dissertation sections. For example, understanding the research question is prerequisite knowledge for understanding the research design, and understanding the variables is prerequisite knowledge for understanding the measures.

² James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 16.

A procedural schema is essential in understanding the relationships among the dissertation sections. For example, understanding the research question is not a prerequisite knowledge for understanding the research design, and understanding the variables is not a prerequisite for understanding the measures.

3. In *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research*, Turabian stressed, “Citation styles differ.” Showing readers that one understands their community values and practices by strictly adhering to the appropriate citation style by displaying an understanding that? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

Citation styles differ in the elements included and the format of these elements, but they aim to give readers the information they need to identify.³

Citation styles do not differ in the elements included and the format of these elements, but they aim to give readers the information they need to identify.

Citation styles differ in the elements included and the format of these elements, but they do not aim to give readers the information they need to identify.

Citation styles differ in the elements included and the format of these elements, but they aim to give readers the information they need not identify.

4. The literature review can provide an adequate foundation for the research questions. In *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research*, Sampson stressed the relationship of critical literature analysis in prior research and problems “with the

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 140.

methods used in prior research (why it is not possible to have confidence in what has been concluded from prior substantially flawed research).” Hence, the critical literature analysis will help identify what? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

- The critical literature analysis will help identify the research content gaps.**⁴
- The critical literature analysis will help identify the research analysis.
- The critical literature analysis will help identify the research literature.
- The critical literature analysis will help identify the research aims and objectives.

5. Referencing the essay to avoid plagiarism is essential to achieving academic excellence, and this issue is closely related to ethics also. Cleenewerck & Gulma in *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* states that “Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course.” So, what to do to avoid plagiarism in academic work? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

- If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks, not just a footnote.**⁵
- If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks with no footnote.
- If you take words from a source, you do not need to use quotation marks, but just a footnote.

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 32.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14.

- You do not need quotation marks or a footnote to avoid word crowdedness if you take words from a source.

6. Alternative forums research work presentations could be helpful to early career or experienced academic writers in many ways. For example, the benefits include confidence building at conferences, exhibitions, and second-person opinions. In *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Turabian states, "Expect questions about data or sources, especially if you didn't cover them much in your talk." What would you do if you got questions about data or sources, mainly if you covered them briefly in your talk or presentation at a conference? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

- Don't snap back an answer reflexively and defensively. Good questions are invaluable, even when they seem hostile. Use them to refine your thinking.**⁶
- Quickly snap back and answer reflexively and defensively. Ignore hostile questions; you don't need them to refine your thinking.
- Don't snap back an answer reflexively and defensively. Ignore hostile questions; you don't need them to refine your thinking.
- Snapback an answer reflexively and defensively, as hostile questions are not helpful.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 133.

7. In *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research*, Sampson stressed the importance “of input from other researchers in the field and the integration of a series of doctoral student research projects.” Chances for successful students' dissertation, completion, and contribution to the literature and body of knowledge could be significant through what type of input? Choose the correct answer from the below options.”

Synergy in dissertation research.⁷

Symbiosis in dissertation research.

Styles in dissertation research.

Syllabus in dissertation research.

8. When you think you can back up your hypothesis, you'll present that hypothesis as your argument's claim. In *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Turabian states that "A claim is an assertion (one sentence or several) that demands support." Therefore evidence-based research arguments require? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

Stating reasons and evidence to back your answers to readers' questions.⁸

Stating reasons but no evidence necessary to back your answers to readers' questions.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 10.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

- Not stating reasons but having evidence to back your answers to readers' questions.
- Not necessarily stating any reasons or evidence to back your answers to readers' questions.

9. An essential lesson for all students is understanding that the academic community and more significant global implications are equally important when choosing their dissertation research topic. In *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research*, Sampson states, "Pursue existing dissertation research goals but be open." Students, while pursuing existing dissertation research goals, should be open to? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

- Serendipity as they may offer you unique opportunities to improve or extend your research.⁹**
- No serendipity as they may not offer unique opportunities to improve or extend your research.
- No serendipity as they may not offer you opportunities to improve or extend your research.
- No serendipity as they may only offer you unique opportunities to improve but not to extend your research.

10. The theoretical and conceptual framework draws on theory, research, and experience and examines the relationship among constructs and ideas. In *Completing Your*

⁹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Qualitative and Quantitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 15.

Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End, Bloomberg and Volpe state, “As such, it is the structure or heuristic that guides your research.” So, the theoretical or conceptual provides for what? Choose the correct answer from the below options.

- The framework provides the study development basis and analysis of study findings.¹⁰**
- The framework provides the study development basis, not the analysis of findings.
- The framework provides the study development basis but an analysis of findings.
- The framework provides neither the study development basis nor the analysis of findings.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 77.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.